

BENEFITS OF GENIUM MICROPROCESSOR CONTROLLED KNEE ON AMBULATION, MOBILITY, ACTIVITIES OF DAILY LIVING AND QUALITY OF LIFE: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

Milana Mileusnic^{1*}, Lena Rettinger¹, Michael Jason Highsmith², Andreas Hahn¹

¹ Department of Clinical Research and Services, Otto Bock HealthCare Products GmbH, Austria.

² Extremity Trauma & Amputation Center of Excellence. U.S. Department of Veteran Affairs, Tampa, FL, USA.

* Email: Milana.Mileusnic@ottobock.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.33137/cpoj.v1i2.32033>

INTRODUCTION

Several years ago, a new microprocessor controlled knee (MPK), Genium, was introduced containing sensors, algorithms and technical solutions that enable a range of new functions to lower limb amputees. We conducted a systematic review to evaluate the effect of the knee on ambulation, mobility, activities of daily living (ADLs) and quality of life (QoL).

METHODS

The systematic review was conducted according to the Prisma Guidelines and recommendations of the State-of-Science Evidence Report Guidelines of the AAOP. Three reviewers conducted the quality assessment independently.

RESULTS

Twelve articles were included in the review and reported of active subjects transitioning from C-Leg to Genium. The overall validity of the evidence was mostly medium and high (Figure 1). Common validity concerns included lack of blinding, incomplete reporting (fatigue & learning effect, attrition rate), effect size calculation, etc. Nine articles focused on ambulation, in particular on level walking, stairs and ramps¹⁻⁹. Biomechanical analysis reported of more physiological and symmetrical gait as well as reduction of loading and compensatory motion on sound side. Four square step test, Amputee Mobility Predictor and step activity derived functional level assessing the mobility were significantly improved⁶. Four publications addressing ADLs reported of significant improvements with values closer to able-bodied subjects (i.e. domains upper-and lower-body strength, balance, coordination, endurance)^{6,9,11,12}. Two articles reported of significant effect of Genium on QoL^{6,10}.

Figure 1. Number and quality of evidence across categories.

CONCLUSION

Quality of evidence is predominantly moderate and high. Genium resulted in more physiological gait, more evenly distributed loading and reduction in compensatory movements. Significant improvements are reported in mobility, QoL and especially safety and ability to conduct ADLs.

SIGNIFICANCE

Additional benefits could be observed with Genium in above knee amputees when compared to standard MPKs. Gait optimization could be relevant considering the long-term risk of secondary physical conditions in the prosthetic wearers.

REFERENCES

1. Aldridge Whitehead JM, et al. Does a Microprocessor-controlled Prosthetic Knee Affect Stair Ascent Strategies in Persons With Transfemoral Amputation? *Clin Orthop Relat Res*; 472, 3093-3101, 2014. DOI:[10.1007/s11999-014-3484-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11999-014-3484-2)

2. Bell EM, et al. Performance of conventional and X2® prosthetic knees during slope descent. *Clin Biomech*; 33, 26-31, 2016. DOI:[10.1016/j.clinbiomech.2016.01.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinbiomech.2016.01.008)
3. Bellmann M, et al. Immediate effects of a new microprocessor-controlled prosthetic knee joint: a comparative biomechanical evaluation. *Arch Phys Med Rehab*; 93, 541-549, 2012. DOI:[10.1016/j.apmr.2011.10.017](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmr.2011.10.017)
4. Bellmann M, et al. Stair ascent with an innovative microprocessor-controlled exoprosthetic knee joint. *Biomed Tech*; 57, 435-444, 2012. DOI:[10.1515/bmt-2011-0029](https://doi.org/10.1515/bmt-2011-0029)
5. Lura DJ et al. Differences in knee flexion between the Genium and C-Leg microprocessor knees while walking on level ground and ramps. *Clin Biomech*; 30, 175-181, 2015. DOI:[10.1016/j.clinbiomech.2014.12.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinbiomech.2014.12.003)
6. Highsmith MJ, et al. Effects of the genium knee system on functional level, stair ambulation, perceptible and economic outcomes in transfemoral amputees. *Technol Innov*; 18, 139-150, 2016. DOI:[10.21300/18.2-3.2016.139](https://doi.org/10.21300/18.2-3.2016.139)
7. Highsmith MJ, et al. Effects of the genium microprocessor knee system on knee moment symmetry during hill walking. *Technol Innov*; 18, 151-157, 2016. doi: [10.21300/18.2-3.2016.151](https://doi.org/10.21300/18.2-3.2016.151)
8. Highsmith MJ, et al. Short and mid-distance walking and posturography with a novel microprocessor knee. *Technol Innov*; 15, 359-368, 2014. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3727/194982413X13844488879302>
9. Hahn A, et al. Analysis of clinically important factors on the performance of advanced hydraulic, microprocessor-controlled exo-prosthetic knee joints based on 899 trial fittings. *Medicine*; 95(45), e5386, 2016. DOI:[10.1097/MD.0000000000005386](https://doi.org/10.1097/MD.0000000000005386)
10. Highsmith MJ, et al. Perceived differences between the genium and the c-leg microprocessor prosthetic knees in prosthetic-related function and quality of life. *Technol Innov*; 15, 369-375, 2014. DOI: [10.3727/194982413X13844489091297](https://doi.org/10.3727/194982413X13844489091297)
11. Highsmith MJ, et al. Functional performance differences between the Genium and C-Leg prosthetic knees and intact knees. *J Rehabil Res Dev*; 53, 753-766, 2016. DOI: [10.1682/JRRD.2014.06.0149](https://doi.org/10.1682/JRRD.2014.06.0149)
12. Kannenberg et al. Activities of Daily Living: Genium Bionic Prosthetic Knee Compared with C-Leg. *J Prosthet Orthot*; 25, 110-117, 2013. doi: [10.1097/JPO.0b013e31829c221f](https://doi.org/10.1097/JPO.0b013e31829c221f)

DISCLOSURE

M Mileusnic, L Rettinger and A Hahn are affiliated with Otto Bock Healthcare Products.